

Technical Report on Mammography Imaging and Breast Cancer Screening

**Prepared by:
Ahmed Adel Nassef**

**Under supervision of:
Dr. Mona Hussien**

**Department of Physics
Faculty of Science
Zagazig University**

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Abstract

This document reviews mammography: its role in breast cancer screening and diagnosis, relevant breast anatomy, imaging principles, and the technical features of mammography equipment. It explains differences between screening and diagnostic mammograms, standard views (craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique), tomosynthesis, and how x-rays form images of fat, fibroglandular tissue, calcifications, and air. Technical considerations covered include the angled tube head, C-arm design, fixed focus-detector distance (65–66 cm), target/filter choices (molybdenum, rhodium, tungsten combinations), focal spot size, compression (typical 100–150 N, max 200 N), anti-scatter grids, and factors affecting spatial resolution needed to detect microcalcifications. The document notes that most images are stored digitally and that tissue sampling is required for definitive diagnosis.

Introduction

Breast cancer is the second most common cancer among women after skin cancer and accounts for 14% of all new cancer cases in the United States.[1] It is most frequently diagnosed in women between 55 and 64 years of age, with the risk increasing as age advances.[2] Early detection improves the likelihood of a cure and reduces treatment-related morbidity. Although breast cancer treatments have continued to advance and contribute to lower mortality rates, early detection through mammographic screening has had the greatest impact on reducing mortality.[3] The American College of Radiology recommends that all women at average risk begin breast cancer screening at age 40.[4]

The diagnosis of breast cancer can be suggested by several imaging modalities, most commonly mammography, breast ultrasound, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). However, a definitive diagnosis requires tissue sampling. Screening for breast cancer is primarily conducted using mammography, and patients with equivocal or suspicious findings on screening require further evaluation with a diagnostic mammogram, ultrasound, breast MRI, biopsy, or a combination of these methods. This article will discuss the techniques and key considerations in performing breast mammography screening [5].

Anatomy of the Breast

The breast consists of fat and fibroglandular tissue, with the parenchyma made up of an intricate network of exocrine glands, ducts, stromal connective tissue, blood vessels, and nerves. It extends from the second to the sixth ribs and is bordered by the sternum medially and the midaxillary line laterally. For easier localization, the breast is commonly divided into quadrants by separating it into medial/lateral and upper/lower sections, using the nipple as the reference point. It is important to note that the upper outer quadrants often contain breast tissue that extends into the axilla. This has significance in mammographic imaging, as complete visualization of this region can be challenging without proper patient positioning. Additionally, one of the main lymphatic drainage pathways of the breast passes through the axilla, where abnormal lymph nodes may be incidentally detected during imaging [5].

Mammography evaluates the breast based on the different attenuation properties of its tissues. Fat attenuates fewer x-rays than fibroglandular tissue and stromal components, appearing gray on mammographic images. Dense mineral deposits, such as skin calcifications or calcifications within a neoplastic lesion, are easily identified and appear bright white. One challenge in mammography is tissue superimposition, where overlapping structures can obscure small masses. To minimize this issue, screening mammograms are obtained in at least two standard views: the craniocaudal (CC) and mediolateral oblique (MLO) views.

Fig 1,2 on the left (CC) View and on the right MLO View [6].

Comparing these two perspectives allows for better differentiation of overlapping structures that may appear superimposed in one view but separate in the other. A

typical mammogram can visualize the skin surface, nipple, major breast ducts, fibroglandular tissue, veins, adipose tissue, muscle, and occasionally lymph nodes [5].

Mammography equipment

Fig 3 Mammography machine [9].

Angled Tube Head:

Because of the anode heel effect, the x-ray beam's strength varies. The cathode side (stronger beam) is aimed at the chest wall to image thicker tissue, while the anode side (weaker beam) faces the nipple for thinner tissue [9].

C-Arm Design:

The x-ray unit is C-shaped, allowing the tube and detector to rotate together and stay aligned [9].

Fixed Focus-Detector Distance (FDD):

The distance between the x-ray source and detector is fixed at about 65–66 cm. This gives a balance between image quality, patient dose, and exposure time [9].

Target and Filter Materials:

- Goal: High contrast and fine detail for detecting small features like micro-calcifications.
- Target: Molybdenum (Mo) produces x-rays of 17–20 keV, ideal for most breasts.
- Filter: Molybdenum filters remove unwanted higher-energy photons.

Alternatives:

- MoMo: Best contrast, higher dose.
- MoRh or RhRh: Slightly higher energy for thicker breasts [9].

Spatial Resolution in Mammography

High spatial resolution is essential to detect tiny details like microcalcifications. It depends on focal spot size, compression, and anti-scatter grids. Smaller **focal spots** produce sharper images. Larger spots cause blurring and make close objects appear merged or distorted [9].

Compression:

Typical force: 100–150 N

Compression improves image quality by:

- Lowering radiation dose
- Reducing scatter
- Spreading breast tissue to reduce overlap
- Decreasing geometric and motion unsharpness
- Making breast thickness more uniform

Anti-Scatter Grids:

Used for standard (contact) images to reduce scatter. For magnified images, a fine focal spot or air gap technique is used instead so a grid isn't needed [9].

How Mammography Work?

Mammograms are used in two main ways.

Screening mammograms

A screening mammogram is employed to detect indicators of breast cancer in women who are asymptomatic (have no breast-related complaints or issues). This procedure involves capturing X-ray images of each breast, generally from two distinct perspectives.

Diagnostic mammograms

Diagnostic mammograms are utilized when a woman presents with breast symptoms or when an abnormality is identified during a screening examination. These mammograms may involve taking additional views (images) of the breast beyond those included in a standard screening. In certain instances, diagnostic mammography is also used for the surveillance of women who have previously received treatment for breast cancer [7].

X-rays are a type of radiation similar to light or radio waves. They can pass through most objects, including the human body. The technologist precisely directs the x-ray beam toward the area of interest. The machine emits a brief burst of radiation that travels through your body. This radiation creates an image on photographic film or a special detector.

Different body parts absorb x-rays to different extents. Dense bone absorbs most of the radiation, while soft tissues (such as muscles, fat, and organs) allow more x-rays to pass through. Consequently, bones appear white on an x-ray, soft tissues appear in shades of gray, and air appears black.

Most x-ray images are stored as digital files, which your doctor can easily access to diagnose and manage your condition.

In standard film and digital mammography, a stationary x-ray tube captures one image from the side and another from above the compressed breast. In breast tomosynthesis, the x-ray tube moves in an arc over the breast, taking multiple images from various angles [8].

Conclusion

Mammography is the primary tool for breast cancer screening and is essential for early detection. High-quality imaging requires appropriate equipment settings (tube/target/filter, fixed FDD), proper technique (positioning, adequate compression), and measures to optimize spatial resolution (small focal spot, anti-scatter strategies). Suspicious findings on mammography require further evaluation with additional imaging and biopsy for a definitive diagnosis.

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